

HEAT TRANSFER STUDY OF THE SECONDARY COOLANT OF THE MOLTEN SALT REACTORS (MSR) WITH ALUMINA NANOFLUID USING DUANGTHONGSUK AND WONGWISES CORRELATION

Joy Surjy Deb, and Md. Mahidul Haque Prodhan

Department of Nuclear Engineering

University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

Dhaka, Bangladesh

joysurjy-03-2015816881@ne.du.ac.bd; prodhan@du.ac.bd

ABSTRACT

This paper analyzes 3% and 4 % volume fraction alumina (Al_2O_3) nanofluid with base fluid FLiBe and FLiNaK using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) methodology by ANSYS. The purpose of the investigation is to choose the better candidate as the secondary coolant in molten salt fuel and coolant-based nuclear power plants for better thermodynamics performances and heat transfer characteristics to ensure more efficiency and economical benefits. This work is inspired by the SAMOFAR project and research on the impact of nanofluids as coolants in PWR (pressurized water reactors) power plants. However, there has not been any substantial research on the impact of the nanofluids as coolants in molten salt reactors and that has been introduced here. For different Reynolds number in a single tube with constant heat flux, Nusselt number (Nu) and forced convective heat transfer coefficient (h) has been analyzed for the both base fluids with and without alumina nanofluid and the data has been compared with Duangthongsuk and Wongwises (D & W) correlation for validation. Overall, both the base fluids FLiBe and FLiNaK showed higher Nusselt number and forced convective heat transfer coefficient with the increasing percentage of the nanofluids compared to the coolant without nanofluids. Moreover, the results of the Nusselt number via simulation have showed substantial similarities with the correlation.

KEYWORDS

MSR, Nanofluid

1. INTRODUCTION

Molten Salt Reactors are one kind of advanced reactors that may operate in high temperature. Due to its non-solid fuel pins or rods there is less risk regarding fuel meltdown compared to conventional PWR [1]. At this moment, several types of researches are being carried on to improve the efficiency of the coolant bearing thermodynamics properties based on their figure of merits in mind. SAMOFAR (Safety Assessment of Molten Salt First Reactor) is one of the leading and prestigious projects regarding MSRs developments. In this project, researchers have proposed FLiBe and FLiNaK till now as coolants [2-8]. Moreover, nanofluids are showing crucial importance as a coolant in nuclear power plants due to their enhanced material properties and sizes through different real-life and simulation-based experiments. Most of the previous studies were to be investigated the thermal and physical properties of LiF(67)-BeF₂(33) (mol%) (FLiBe) and LiF(46.5)-NaF(11.5)-KF(42) (mol%) (FLiNaK) [1- 2], [9-10]. For example, Bahri et al. [1] investigated the physical properties of these two molten salts in terms of their application as coolant, and fuel solvent and showed their comparative benefits and drawbacks. However, Charles et al. [2]

discussed a technology gap for the development and deployment of the MSRs. For the single tube, the forced convective heat transfer performance of FLiNaK salt has been experimentally conducted by Hoffman et al. [11]. Moreover, Bang, Kwang-Hyun along with others et al. [12] investigated FLiNaK and gas, where a double pipe heat exchanger was established using small diameter tubes. Similarly, Williams et al. [9] and Williams et al. [10] stated that, molten salts characteristics showed to be significant candidates due to their positive and noteworthy performances in high temperatures. Primarily, mainly for SAMOFAR project as a fuel salt, which is also primary coolant two main options ($\text{LiF-ThF}_4\text{-}^{233}\text{UF}_4$) and $\text{LiF-ThF}_4\text{-}^{235}\text{UF}_4\text{-}((\text{Pu-MA})\text{F}_3)$ are recommended [4-5]. Similarly, Silverman et al. [13] analyzed the forced convective heat transfer of one fuel salt $\text{LiF-BeF}_2\text{-ThF}_4\text{-UF}_4$, while E. Merle investigated another fuel considering the SAMOFAR project for the better candidate [6]. Subsequently, substantial CFD based researches have been carried on by different academicians to improve heat exchanger, as well as to investigate the thermal performances of the fuel and coolant salts for the future development of MSRs, regarding design, construction materials of vessels and heat exchangers, and coolants [7-8], [14-17]. Moreover, several types of research were also conducted to find out the thermal-hydraulics performances of the coolant in designed shell and tube heat exchangers, along with improving the heat exchangers for better heat transfer conditions [18-19]. Uğur Köse along with others et al. [20] have investigated, and proposed a heat exchanger design for SAMOFAR using ANSYS FLUENT commercial code.

Chen-Wei Chi et al. [21] investigated Nusselt number of the molten salt $\text{LiF}(46.5)\text{-NaF}(11.5)\text{-KF}(42)$ using Gnielinski and Hausen correlations, that are considered more appropriate than Dittus-Boelter in terms of molten salt. Hausen et al. [22] and Gnielinski et al. [23] tried to produce a new empirical correlation apart from Dittus-Boelter, that might be useful for high Reynolds number and Prandtl number fluid, which is later used for the investigation of the molten salt thermal properties. Apurba et al. [24] used Hausen and Gnielinski correlations for evaluating molten nitrate heat transfer. However, Ambrosek et al. [25] recently re-evaluated the FLiNaK test data with an updated formula, which eventually showed an improved relation according to the Dittus-Boelter correlation, with a negligible 15 percent error.

Nanofluids are also contributing substantially for the future nuclear industry, and its research arena for safe operation as well as ensuring enhanced heat transfer rate. Pak & Cho et al. [26] led an investigation with alumina nanofluids to prove that Dittus-Boelter and Gnielinski correlations are not up to the mark to calculate the Nusselt number of the nanofluid. Hence, they mentioned a new correlation for this calculation. Jaafar et al. [27] calculated Nusselt number of the nanofluids using Pak & Cho and D & W correlations. After comparing between them, it was shown that the latter showed more efficient result. Wen and Ding [28] examined alumina nanoparticles and de-ionized water for heat transfer calculation and eventually concluded that heat transfer increases using nanofluid. Allahyari et al. [29] studied laminar mixed convection of alumina water by heating the top half surface of a Cu tube horizontally and concluded that the heat transfer coefficient rises with the increased concentration of nanoparticles. Moreover, different notable researchers tried to find out the relation between the Brownian motion and increased heat transfer of nanofluids. Therefore, they proposed different mathematical model after their substantial investigation to justify their claims regarding the importance of Brownian motion in terms of increased heat transfer characteristics of nanofluids [30-38]. Hadad et al. [39] investigated the thermal-hydraulic properties of Al_2O_3 + water nanofluid as the coolant in a VVER-1000 nuclear reactor core, by using a CFD code considering a finite volume method for single-phase and two-phase mixture models to find convective heat transfer coefficient, and pressure drop. Similarly, a study done by S. J. Kim et al. [40] nanofluids are used as the main reactor coolant for pressurized water reactors (PWRs), which could be used to enhance economic performance with at least 32% higher critical heat flux (CHF) and a 20% power density commensurate with current PWRs without varying the fuel assembly design and without decreasing the margin to CHF. Nonetheless, to date, not a significant amount of experiments has been conducted with a mixture of nanofluid with FLiBe or FLiNaK as a nuclear coolant. Therefore, this paper is going to investigate this promising aspect of nanofluids in molten salt reactor considering the fuel salt and secondary coolant salt for SAMOFAR project.

2. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

2.1. Governing Equations

This work assumed several significant sectors before proceeding the simulation. Firstly, the simulation was conducted under steady-state condition and the vital governing equations that were used to simulate the thermal-hydraulic characteristics include the continuity, momentum, and energy equations [41-42]. Besides, the appropriate turbulence model was integrated to conduct the simulation. For steady state conditions, the above-mentioned equation can be described as below:

2.1.1. Continuity equation

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho u) = 0 \quad (1)$$

2.1.2. Momentum equation

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho u u) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \tau \quad (2)$$

τ is the stress tensor (described below),

$$\tau = \mu [(2\nabla u) - 2/3\nabla \cdot u] \quad (3)$$

2.1.3. Energy equation

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho u h) = \nabla \cdot ((\Gamma / C_p) \nabla u) \quad (4)$$

2.2. Turbulence Model

Since the Reynolds number is greater than 2300 in pipe flow, the influence of turbulence must be considered. In the present work, standard k- ϵ turbulence model is employed. The standard k - ϵ model is employed that includes two transport equations that are turbulence kinetic energy k and dissipation rate of turbulence energy ϵ . These two parameters k and ϵ can be found by solving the following equations [41-42].

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho k u_i) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} [(\mu + \mu_t / \sigma_k) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j}] + G_k - \rho \epsilon \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho \epsilon u_i) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} [(\mu + \mu_t / \sigma_\epsilon) \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial x_j}] + C_{\epsilon 1} (\epsilon / k) G_k - C_{\epsilon 2} (\epsilon^2 / k) \rho \quad (6)$$

μ_t is the turbulence viscosity where, $\mu_t = \rho C_\mu (k^2/\epsilon)$

G_k is the production of turbulent kinetic energy and $G_k = \rho \overline{u'v'u'v} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i}$

C_{ϵ_1} , C_{ϵ_2} , C_μ , σ_k and σ_ϵ are empirical constants where $C_{\epsilon_1}=1.44$, $C_{\epsilon_2}=1.92$, $C_\mu=0.9$, $\sigma_k=1$ and $\sigma_\epsilon=1.3$

3. SIMULATION

3.1. Geometry, Mesh and BoundaryCondition

This work investigates a preliminary concept in terms of a circular pipe flow. Though in real life in heat-exchanger the heat transfer process is more complicated, it demonstrates a brief analysis on the effect of alumina nanofluids with FLiBe and FLiNaK as secondary coolant regarding the Nusselt numbers, and convective heat transfer coefficients of the coolants. For meshing multi-zoned meshing method with Hexa mapped mesh type is used. In the meshing section also inflation is controlled to ensure first layer thickness competence and increase meshing quality. As the standard k epsilon method is introduced, the wall Y^+ value is adjusted between 30-100 bearing the local fluid velocity of the coolants, and thus the meshing is employed for this simulation. The SIMPLE method is employed to couple velocity and pressure here. According to different previous works, nanofluids can be treated as single-phase models for low volume fractions [43-44]. As the volume fraction of 3% and 4% are considered for this work that is negligible; therefore, the single-phase method is employed here. In this investigation, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) is used as an analysis tool, it utilizes the continuity equation, momentum equation, energy equation, and standard K-epsilon turbulence model. All the simulations presented in this work are calculated by the CFD code FLUENT 18.1. A single circular pipe heat-exchanger has been introduced to determine the better secondary coolant out of the proposed candidates above and the dimensions have been adapted according to Hoffman [11]. For this simulation,

Inner diameter of the pipe=6.225 mm; outer diameter = 9.525 mm; thickness= 1.65 mm
Length of the pipe= 609.6mm and constant wall flux= 1250000 Wm⁻²

Primarily, the Nusselt Number (Nu) and forced convective heat transfer coefficient (h) have been calculated for a single pipe. As the length is more than 60 times of the diameter so the flow can be considered fully developed. The Pipe was also divided into two regions (entrance length region and fully developed region). According to different studies the inlet velocity of the secondary coolant salt should be between 2.5-5 ms⁻¹ [20].

Therefore, three separate investigations have been conducted considering 4 ms⁻¹, 4.5 ms⁻¹ and 5 ms⁻¹ inlet velocity for both 4% Al₂O₃ nanofluids based FLiBe (FLiBe-4), and 4% Al₂O₃ nanofluids based FLiNaK (FLiNaK-4) cases. Thus, in terms of FLiBe-4 and FLiNaK, three different Reynolds number (Re) were found for each case based on their three different inlet velocities. These were 6120.96, 6886.07 and 7651.19 for the inlet velocities of 4, 4.5, and 5 ms⁻¹ respectively; whereas, in terms of FLiNaK-4 it was 14087.64, 15848.6 and 17609.5. Later for FLiBe, FLiBe with 3% Al₂O₃ (FLiBe-3) and FLiBe with 4% Al₂O₃, Nusselt number (Nu), forced convective heat transfer coefficient (h) have been measured for Re = 6120.96, 6886.07 and 7651.19; while, same simulation has been continued for FLiNaK, FLiNaK with 3% Al₂O₃ (FLiNaK-3) and FLiNaK with 4% Al₂O₃ for Reynolds number 14087.64, 15848.6 and 17609.5.

3.2. Thermal Properties

For Pipe material it has been suggested to use hastelloy-n alloy for its higher melting point, as well as better strength and good physical properties since MSR's need to operate in higher temperature [9-11] [45]. The thermal properties of the fuel salt, secondary coolant candidates and hastelloy-n alloy are selected by different empirical equations and data from several studies [6], [45-47]. Elsa Merle et al. [6] represented empirical equations to determine thermal and physical properties for the fuel salt which is calculated for temperature 1023K for this experiment. Moreover, for hastelloy-n alloy, this data is selected from another study [46]. In addition the thermal and physical data of FLiBe and FLiNaK has been derived from another study for 973K. [45]. According to the above mentioned work the thermal properties of FLiBe, FLiNaK and Hastelloy-n alloy is given below for 700°C, whereas; for alumina nanofluids the data is considered at 25°C [47].

Table I. Thermal properties

Name	Specific Heat (J. kg ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹)	Thermal Conductivity (W. m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹)	Density (Kg. m ⁻³)	Viscosity (Pa. s)
FLiBe	2397.73	1.1163	1938.06	0.0055
FLiNaK	2011.7	0.9050	2018.9	0.0025
Hastelloy-n	578	23.6	8860	
Alumina	773	36	3880	

Similarly, for 3% and 4% alumina nanofluid with base fluid molten salt coolant (FLiBe and FLiNaK) all the thermo-physical properties are derived from the following equations [48].

$$\rho_{nf} = (1 - \phi) \rho_{bf} + \phi \times \rho_p \quad (7)$$

$$(\rho C_p)_{nf} = (1 - \phi) (\rho C_p)_{bf} + \phi \times (\rho C_p)_p \quad (8)$$

$$\mu_{nf} = (123\phi^2 + 7.3\phi + 1) \times \mu_{bf} \quad (9)$$

$$k_{nf} = (4.97\phi^2 + 2.72\phi + 1) \times k_{bf} \quad (10)$$

Here ϕ is the volume percentage of the nanoparticles in the base fluid, whereas; nf and bf mean nanofluid and base fluid respectively.

4. RESULT & DISCUSSION

The six candidates coolants with and without nanofluids are forced to be conveyed through the circular single pipe with constant heat flux. For the first experiment Nu and h has been calculated properly through numerical simulation as these are crucial parameter and properties for heat transfer, later the data of Nusselt Number regarding nanofluids has been compared with Duangthongsuk and Wongwises (D & W) correlation as Gnielinski correlation is not appropriated for nanofluids [49]. In the following equation, Φ means the volume percentage of the nanofluids according to D & W correlation [49].

$$Nu = 0.074 Re^{0.707} Pr^{0.385} \phi^{0.074} \quad (11)$$

$$Nu = \frac{hD}{k} \quad (12)$$

**Figure 1. Reynolds Number VS Forced Convective Heat Transfer Coefficient
In Case of FLiBe (With Or Without Nanofluids).**

According to Figure-1, for $Re=7651.19$, whenever alumina nanofluid volume percentage is increased the inlet velocity of the secondary coolants FLiBe-3 (FLiBe with 3% alumina) increases as well as FLiBe-4 (FLiBe with 4% alumina) has experienced the highest inlet velocity among the three candidates and it is 4.5 ms^{-1} and 5 ms^{-1} respectively for FLiBe-3 and FLiBe-4 compared with 3.49 ms^{-1} for FLiBe. For the heat transfer coefficient with the numerically simulated solution FLiBe-4 has showed the highest value of 16663.7 Wm^{-2} , followed by 15718.5 Wm^{-2} for FLiBe-3 and the lowest for FLiBe with 13503.3 Wm^{-2} .

Similarly, for $Re=6886.07$, whenever alumina nanofluid volume percentage is increased the inlet velocity of the secondary coolants FLiBe-3 increases as well as FLiBe-4 experiences the highest inlet velocity among the three candidates and it is 4.05 ms^{-1} and 4.5 ms^{-1} respectively for FLiBe-3 and FLiBe-4 compared with 3.14 ms^{-1} for FLiBe. For the heat transfer coefficient with the numerically simulated solution FLiBe-4 has showed the highest value of 15260 Wm^{-2} , followed by 14394.4 Wm^{-2} for FLiBe-3 and the lowest for FLiBe with 12361.7 Wm^{-2} .

In addition, for $Re=6120.96$, whenever alumina nanofluid volume percentage is increased the inlet velocity of the secondary coolants FLiBe-3 increases as well as FLiBe-4 experiences the highest inlet velocity among the three candidates and it is 3.6 ms^{-1} and 4 ms^{-1} respectively for FLiBe-3 and FLiBe-4 compared with 2.79 ms^{-1} for FLiBe. For the heat transfer coefficient with the numerically simulated solution FLiBe-4 has showed the highest value of 13837.5 Wm^{-2} , followed by 13051.9 Wm^{-2} for FLiBe-3 and the lowest for FLiBe with 11204.6 Wm^{-2} .

The following Figure-2 illustrates the comparison among FLiBe-3 and FLiBe-4 based on Nusselt number output with varying input velocity. For $Re=7651.19$, FLiBe-4 has showed the highest value of 83.21, followed by 80.71 for FLiBe-3. However, D & W correlation overestimated the values with 92 and 87.51 respectively.

Whereas for $Re=6886.07$, FLiBe-4 has showed the highest value of 76.2, followed respectively by FLiBe-3 with accompanying value of 73.91. However, D & W correlation overestimated the values with 85.4 and 81.22 respectively.

Similarly, for $Re=6120.96$, FLiBe-4 has showed the highest value of 69.1, followed respectively by FLiBe-3 with accompanying value of 67.01. However, D & W correlation overestimated the values with 78.58 and 74.73 respectively.

**Figure 2. Comparison Between Simulation & Correlation
In Terms Of Nusselt Number For FLiBe.**

According to Figure-3, for $Re=17609.5$, whenever alumina nanofluid volume percentage is increased the inlet velocity of the secondary coolants FLiNaK-3 (FLiNaK with 3% alumina) increases as well as FLiNaK-4 (FLiNaK with 4% alumina) experiences the highest inlet velocity among the three candidates and it is 4.5 ms^{-1} and 5 ms^{-1} respectively for FLiNaK-3 and FLiNaK-4 compared with 3.5 ms^{-1} for

FLiNaK. For the heat transfer coefficient with the numerically simulated solution FLiNaK-4 showed the highest value of 19178 Wm^{-2} , followed by 17989.8 Wm^{-2} for FLiNaK-3 and the lowest for FLiNaK with 15294.7 Wm^{-2} . In the same way, for $Re=15848.6$, whenever alumina nanofluid volume percentage is increased the inlet velocity of the secondary coolants FLiNaK-3 (FLiNaK with 3% alumina) increases as well as FLiNaK-4 (FLiNaK with 4% alumina) has experienced the highest inlet velocity among the three candidates and it is 4.05 ms^{-1} and 4.5 ms^{-1} respectively for FLiNaK-3 and FLiNaK-4 compared with 3.15 ms^{-1} for FLiNaK. For the heat transfer coefficient with the numerically simulated solution FLiNaK-4 has showed the highest value of 17563.6 Wm^{-2} , followed by 16476 Wm^{-2} for FLiNaK-3 and the lowest for FLiNaK with 14008.7 Wm^{-2} . Similarly, for $Re=14087.64$, whenever alumina nanofluid volume percentage is increased the inlet velocity of the secondary coolants FLiNaK-3 (FLiNaK with 3% alumina) increases as well as FLiNaK-4 (FLiNaK with 4% alumina) has experienced the highest inlet velocity among the three candidates and it is 3.6 ms^{-1} and 4 ms^{-1} respectively for FLiNaK-3 and FLiNaK-4 compared with 2.8 ms^{-1} for FLiNaK. For the heat transfer coefficient with the numerically simulated solution FLiNaK-4 has showed the highest value of 15921.4 Wm^{-2} , followed by 14935.9 Wm^{-2} for FLiNaK-3 and the lowest for FLiNaK with 12700.2 Wm^{-2} .

**Figure 3. Reynolds Number VS Forced Convective Heat Transfer Coefficient
In Case of FLiNaK (With Or Without Nanofluids).**

The following Figure-4 illustrates the comparison among FLiNaK-3 and FLiNaK-4 based on Nusselt number output with varying input velocity. For $Re=17609.5$, FLiNaK-4 has showed the highest value of 118.12 , followed by 113.93 for FLiNaK-3. However, D & W correlation overestimated the values with

124.05 and 117.97 respectively. Whereas, for $Re=15848.6$, FLiNaK-4 has showed the highest value of 108.18, followed by FLiNaK-3 with 104.31. However, D & W correlation overestimated the values with 115.15 and 109.5 respectively. Whereas, for $Re=14087.64$, FLiNaK-4 has showed the highest value of 98.06, followed by FLiNaK-3 with 94.59. However, D & W correlation overestimated the values with 105.95 and 100.75 respectively.

**Figure 4. Comparison Between Simulation & Correlation
In Terms Of Nusselt Number For FLiNaK.**

From Figure-2 and Figure-4 all the data has slightly overly estimated the theoretical data for the same Reynolds number according to D & W correlation and the error percentage is 5-8 % in case of FLiNaK; whereas, the error percentage is around 8-14% in case of FLiBe. Therefore, the simulated result can be trustworthy for reaching a verdict. The reason behind the overestimation might be the difference between simulation and real life experiment. However, with further improved assumption and competent modeling in terms of simulation might give higher accurate results similar to the correlations. Moreover, it can be evident that with higher Reynolds number the simulation result and the correlation have less difference that might indicate the range of Reynolds number for which this correlation can predict the Nusselt number properly compared to simulation. According to these figures and the following table, it can be illustrated that, for the same Reynolds number the convective heat transfer coefficient was increased whenever the nanofluids' percentage was increased. The main reason behind is the increasing trend of the density which eventually helped to transfer heat more precisely.

Table II. Data: simulation and correlation

Candidate	Reynolds Number	Inlet Velocity (m. s ⁻¹)	Nusselt Number (simulation)	Nusselt Number (correlation)	Forced Convective Heat Transfer Coefficient (W. m ⁻² . K ⁻¹)
FLiBe	7651.19	3.49	75.3		13503.3
FLiBe-3	7651.19	4.5	80.71	87.51	15718.5
FLiBe-4	7651.19	5	83.21	92	16663.7
FLiBe	6886.07	3.14	68.93		12361.7
FLiBe-3	6886.07	4.05	73.91	81.22	14394.4
FLiBe-4	6886.07	4.5	76.2	85.4	15260
FLiBe	6120.96	2.79	62.48		11204.6
FLiBe-3	6120.96	3.6	67.01	74.73	13051.9
FLiBe-4	6120.96	4	69.1	78.58	13837.5
FLiNaK	17609.5	3.5	105.2		15294.7
FLiNaK-3	17609.5	4.5	113.93	117.97	17989.8
FLiNaK-4	17609.5	5	118.12	124.05	19178
FLiNaK	15848.6	3.15	96.36		14008.7
FLiNaK-3	15848.6	4.05	104.31	109.5	16476
FLiNaK-4	15848.6	4.5	108.18	115.15	17563.6
FLiNaK	14087.64	2.8	87.36		12700.2
FLiNaK-3	14087.64	3.6	94.59	100.75	14935.9
FLiNaK-4	14087.64	4	98.06	105.95	15921.4

To summarize with the increasing nanofluid percentage in both base fluid, the Nu and h have showed increasing trend with positive outputs. The reason behind the positive impact of the nanofluids can be explained analyzing the positive impact of nonofluids' Brownian motion and higher wettability of the nanofluids compared to base fluids. As, the Brownian motion in nanofluids is significant compared to base fluids due to their nano-scale molecular presence, it transfer heat more conveniently compared to the base fluids. Moreover, due to its' higher surface to volume ratio, it can easily create and continue contact between the solid surface of the pipe more conveniently and efficiently compared with the base fluid, thus increase the heat transfer compared with the latter one.

5. CONTRIBUTION TO MOLTEN SALT REACTORS

According to this study, nanofluids percentages affect the heat transfer performance of the secondary coolant of MSR in a positive way for the same Reynold's number. Therefore, if we use FLiBe or FLiNaK with alumina nanofluids instead of without nanofluids, the coolant will extract out higher amount of heat from the primary coolant circuit and eventually will transfer more heat to the power conversion cycle. Consequently, the efficiency of the cycle will be increased. In addition, if we can extract out more heat from the primary circuit, it will ensure and increase the safety feature simultaneously. Moreover, as the overall heat transfer coefficient of the heat exchanger depends on the inner and outer fluids' (primary and secondary coolants in case of MSR) forced convective heat transfer coefficient, the overall heat

transfer coefficient will be higher in terms of using nanofluids. Therefore, less area of heat exchanger will be required. This will result in needing less amount of materials for constructing heat exchanger compared to present proposals. At present, hastelloy-n alloy or nickel based alloys are the primary candidates for the heat exchangers' materials in MSRs. However, these materials are expensive. Therefore, if we use nanofluids this will reduce the amount of materials that will be needed for heat exchanger. In a result, this will introduce an economic benefit.

6. CONCLUSION

This study has found out that, in the case of the increasing volume percentage of the nanofluids the coolants showed higher thermal performance in terms of heat convection that is a praiseworthy and notable output. Moreover, this work justifies the utility of D&W correlation in terms of the usages of alumina nanofluids in MSRs. Therefore, overall this study produces a significant outcome in terms of MSRs future with nanofluids.

Though, this study demonstrates an economic benefit regarding heat exchangers' materials, the cost-benefit analysis in terms of nanofluids should be investigated. More thorough and contemplated research needs to be conducted regarding this two consideration. Moreover, this study does not investigate the pressure drop. Therefore, more extensive research needs to be performed to analyze the required pumping power. This will also influence the economic analysis regarding the cost of pumps.

To summarize, this study illustrates a preliminary positive idea linking nanofluids to MSRs as coolants. Nevertheless, neutronic analysis should be conducted. In this paper, no neutronic analysis has been investigated. Furthermore, as this study investigates flow in a single tube with some assumption, for more precise analysis, heat exchanger model should be integrated. With heat exchanger, more precise real life neutronic and thermal analysis, in other words experimental validation should be appreciated.

7. NOMENCLATURE

Governing Equations

u = fluid velocity

ρ = fluid density

η = stress tensor

Γ = fluid thermal conductivity

k = turbulence kinetic energy

ε = turbulence dissipation rate

μ_t = turbulence viscosity

G_k = production of turbulence kinetic energy

Result and Discussion

h = forced convective heat transfer coefficient

D = diameter of the pipe

k = thermal conductivity of the fluid

Re = Reynolds number

Pr = Prandtl number

8. REFERENCES

1. S. Cantor, J. W. Cooke, A. S. Dworkin, G. D. Robbins, R. E. Thomas, and G. M. Watson, "Physical properties of molten-salt reactor fuel, coolant, and flush salts" Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Tennessee, USA, Tech. Rep. TM-2316, 1968.
2. C. N. Aniza, C. B. Bahri, W.M. Al Areqi, M.I.F. Mohd Ruf, and A. Ab. Majid, "Characteristic of molten fluoride salt system LiF-BeF₂ (flibe) and LiF-NaF-KF (flinak) as coolant and fuel carrier in molten salt reactor" in AIP Conference Proceedings, Paper 1799, 040008, 2017.
3. C. W. Forsberg, "Molten-salt-reactor technology gapsk" *Proc. ICAPP*, Paper 6295, Reno NV, USA, 4 - 8 June, 2006.
4. D. Gerardin, M. Allibert, D. Heuer, A. Laureau, E. Merle-Lucotte, and C. Seuvre, "Design evolutions of molten salt fast reactor" in *Int. Conf. Fast React. Relat. Fuel Cycles Next Gener. Nucl. Syst. Sustain. Dev. Yekaterinburg, Russia., June 26-29, 2017*.
5. M. Tano, P. Rubiolo, and O. Doche, "Progress in modeling solidification in molten salt coolants" in *Modelling and Simulation in Materials Science and Engineering 25*, 2017.
6. E. Merle-lucotte, D. Heuer, M. Allibert, M. Brovchenko, V. Ghetta, A. Laureau, and P. Rubiolo, "Preliminary design assessment of the molten salt fast reactor" in *European Nuclear Conference ENC2012, Manchester, UK, December, 2012*.
7. M. DIEUAIDE, "SAMOFAR molten salt fast reactor reprocessing unit design" [Online]. Available: www.kth.se [Accessed May, 2018].
8. V. Di Marcello, and A. Cammi, L. Luzzi "Analysis of coupled dynamics of molten salt reactors" in *Proceedings of the COMSOL Conference 2008, Hannover, 2008*.
9. D. F. Williams, "Assessment of candidate molten salt coolants for the ngnp/hi heat transfer loop" Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Tennessee, USA, Tech. Rep. TM-2006/69, 2006.
10. D. F. Williams, L. M. Toth, and K. T. Clarno, "Assessment of candidate molten salt coolants for the advanced high-temperature reactor (AHTR)" Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Tennessee, USA, Tech. Rep. TM-2006/12, 2006.
11. H. W. Hoffman, and J. Lones, "Fused salt heat transfer, part II: forced convection heat transfer in circular tubes containing NaF-KF-LiF eutectic" Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Tennessee, USA, Tech. Rep. 1777, 1955.
12. Bang, Kwang-Hyun, Hwang, In-Seon, Jeong, Hui-Seong, Kim, Kyung-Kyu, Choi, and Ok-Keun "An experimental study on the flow and heat transfer of flinak molten salt in small channels for the application to the VHTR intermediate heat exchanger" in *Proceedings of international congress on advances in nuclear power plants*, 2009.
13. M. D. Silverman, W. R. Huntley, and H. E. Robertson, "Heat transfer measurements in a forced convection loop with two molten-fluoride salts: LiF-BeF₂-ThF₄-UF₄ and EUTECTIC NaBF₄-NaF" Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Tennessee, USA, Tech. Rep. TM- 5335, 1976.
14. A. Di Ronco, A. Cammi, and S. Lorenzi "Preliminary analysis and design of the heat exchangers for the molten salt fast reactor" *Nuclear Engineering and Technology* 52, July, 2019.
15. A. Kasam, and E. Shwageraus "Approximate heat transfer solution for the breed and burn molten salt reactor" in *M&C 2017 - International Conference on Mathematics & Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science & Engineering*, Jeju, Korea, April 16- 20, 2017.
16. P. R. Rubiolo, M. T. Retamales, V. E. Ghetta, and J. Giraud "High temperature thermal hydraulics modeling of a molten salt: application to a molten salt fast reactor (MSFR)" in *ESAIM: PROCEEDINGS AND SURVEYS*, 2017, Vol. 58, p. 98-117, 08 November 2017. [Online serial]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1051/proc/201758098/>. [Accessed Nov. 8, 2017].
17. L. Luzzi, M. Aufiero, A. Cammi, and C. Fiorina, "Thermo-hydrodynamics of internally heated molten salts for innovative nuclear reactors", MA: Hydrodynamics - Theory and Model, Dr. Jin - Hai Zheng (Ed.), ISBN: 978-953-51-0130-7, InTech, March, 2012. [E-book] Available: <http://www.intechopen.com/books/hydrodynamicstheory-and-model/thermo-hydrodynamics-of>

- internally-heated-molten-salts-for-innovative-nuclear-reactors18. P. Fraas, and M. E. Laverne, “Parametric survey of the effects of major parameters on the design of fuel-to-inert-salt heat mchanges for the msbr” Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Tennessee, USA, Tech. Rep. TM-2952, November, 1971
19. E. Bettis, R. J. Braatz, G. A. Cristy, D. A. Dyslin, O. A. Kelly, T. W. Pickel, L. R. Shobe, A. E. Spaller, and W. C. Stoddart, “Design study of a heat-exchange system for one msbr concept” Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Tennessee, USA, Tech. Rep. TM-1545, September, 1967.
20. U. Köse1, U. Koç1, L. B. Erbay, E. Ögüt, and H. Ayhan1, “Regular article Heat exchanger design studies for molten salt fast reactor” in *EPJ Nuclear Science Technology* 5, 12, 2019.
21. C. W. Chi, Y. M. Ferng, B. S. Pei, and J. H. Liang, “Investigating thermal-hydraulic characteristic of molten fluoride salt in a circular pipe using a cfd methodology”, *19th International Conference on Nuclear Engineering*, Chiba, Japan, May 16-19, 2011.
22. H. Hausen, “Neue gleichungen für die wärmeübertragung bei freier oder erzwungener stromung (new equations for heat transfer in free or forced flow)”, *Allg. Wärmetech.*, pp. 75–79, 1959.
23. V. Gnielinski, “New equations for heat and mass transfer in turbulent pipe and channel flow”, *International Chemical Engineering*, vol. 16 (2), pp. 359-367, 1976.
24. A. K. Das, M. M. Clark, B. C. Teigen, W. A. Fiveland, and M. H. Anderson, “Heat transfer behavior of molten nitrate salt”, in *AIP Conference Proceedings, SolarPACES 2015*.
25. J. Ambrosek, M. Anderson, K. Sridharan, and T. Allen, “Current status of knowledge of the fluoride salt (FLiNaK) heat transfer” *Nuclear Technology*, vol. 165(2), pp.166–173, 2009.
26. B.C. Pak, and Y.I. Cho, “Hydrodynamic and heat transfer study of dispersed fluids with submicron metallic oxide particles”, *Exp. Heat Transfer*, vol. 11. No. 2, pp. 151-170, 1998.
27. J. Albadr, S. Tayal, and M. Alasadi, “Heat transfer through heat exchanger using Al₂O₃ nanofluid at different concentrations”, *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, No. 1, pp. 38-44, 2013.
28. D. S. Wen, and Y. Ding, “Experimental Investigation into Convective Heat Transfer of Nanofluids at the entrance region under laminar flow conditions” *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 47, no. 24, pp. 5181-5188, November, 2004.
29. S. Allahyari, A. Behzadmehr, and S. M. H. Sarvari, “Conjugate heat transfer of laminar mixed convection of a nanofluid through a horizontal tube with circumferentially non-uniform heating” *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, vol. 50, no.10, pp. 1963-1972, October, 2011.
30. K. V. Sharma, L. S. Sundar, and P. K. Sarma, “Estimation of heat transfer coefficient and friction factor in the transition flow with low volume concentration of Al₂O₃ nanofluid flowing in a circular tube and with twisted tape insert”, *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 503-507, 2009.
31. J. Buongiorno, “Convective transport in nanofluids”, *Journal of Heat Transfer*, vol. 128, no. 3, 2006.
32. J. Koo, and C. Kleinstreuer, “A new thermal conductivity model for nanofluids”, *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, vol. 6, no. 6, 2004.
33. P. Keblinski, W. Evans, and J. Fish, “Role of Brownian motion hydrodynamics on nanofluid thermal conductivity”, *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 88, no. 9, 2006.
34. M. R. Azizian, H. S. Aybar, and T. Okutucu, “Effect of nanoconvection due to Brownian motion on thermal conductivity of nanofluids”, in *Proceeding of the 7th IASME/WSEAS International Conference on Heat Transfer, Thermal Engineering and Environment (HTE'09)*, pp. 53–56, Moscow, Russia, 2009.
35. S. P. Jang and S. U. S. Choi, “Effects of various parameters on nanofluid thermal conductivity”, *Journal of Heat Transfer*, vol.129, no. 5, 2007.
36. D. H. Kumar, H. E. Patel, V. R. R. Kumar, T. Sundararajan, T. Pradeep, and S. K. Das, “Model for heat conduction in nanofluids”, *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 93, no. 14, 2004.
37. H. E. Patel, T. Sundararajan, T. Pradeep, A. Dasgupta, N. Dasgupta, and S. K. Das, “A micro convection model for thermal conductivity of nanofluids”, *Pramana*, vol. 65, no. 5, 2005.38. R. S.

- Vajjha and D. K. Das, “Experimental determination of thermal conductivity of three nanofluids and development of new correlations”, *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 52, no. 21-22, 2009.
39. K. Hadad, A. Rahimian, and M.R. Nematollahi, “Numerical study of single and two- phase models of water/Al₂O₃ nanofluid turbulent forced convection flow in VVER-1000 nuclear reactor” in *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 60, pp.287-294, 2013.
40. J. Boungiorno, L.W. Hu, S.J. Kim, R. Hannink, B. Truong, and E. Forrest, “Nanofluids for enhanced economics and safety of nuclear reactors: an evaluation of the potential features, issues, and research gaps” *Nuclear Technology*, vol. 162, pp. 80-91, April 2017.
41. Y. Xuan, and Q. Li, “Investigation on convective heat transfer and flow features of nanofluids,” *Journal of Heat Transfer*, vol. 125, no. 1, pp. 151-155, 2003.
42. Y. Qiu, M. Li, M. Li, H. Zhang, B. Ning, “Numerical and experimental study on heat transfer and flow features of representative molten salts for energy applications in turbulent tube flow”, *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 135, pp.732-74, 2019.
43. L.S. Sundar and M. K. Singh, “ Convective heat transfer and friction factor correlations of nanofluid in a tube and with inserts: A review”, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 20, p.p 23-35, 2013.
44. X. Wang and A. S. Mujumdar, “A REVIEW ON NANOFLUIDS - PART I: THEORETICAL AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATIONS”, *Brazilian Journal of Chemical Engineering*, vol. 25, no. 04, pp. 613-630, 2008.
45. M. S. Sohal, M. A. Ebner, P. Sabharwall, and P. Sharpe “Engineering database of liquid salt thermophysical and thermochemical properties” Idaho National Laboratory, Idaho, USA. Tech. Rep. INL/EXT-10-18297, March, 2010.
46. R. J. Kedl, “Fluid dynamic studies of the molten-salt reactor experiment (msre) core” Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Tennessee, USA, Tech. Rep. tm- 3229, November, 1970.
47. D. P. Kulkarni, D. K. Das, and G. A. Chukwu, “Temperature dependent rheological property of copper oxide nanoparticles suspension (nanofluid),” *Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 1150–1154, 2006
48. Bianco, V., Chiacchio, F., Manca, O., Nardini, S., 2009. “Numerical investigation of nanofluids forced convection in circular tubes,” *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol.29, pp.3632-3642.
49. W. Duangthongsuk , and S. Wongwises, “Heat transfer enhancement and pressure drop characteristics of TiO₂-water nanofluid in a double-tube counter flow heat exchanger”, *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, Vol. 52, No. 7-8, pp. 2059-2067, 2009.